

Automated Analysis of Fluorescence Kinetics in Single-Molecule Localization Microscopy Data Reveals Protein Stoichiometry

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Keywords

Single-molecule localization microscopy; super-resolution microscopy; protein quantification;
deep neural network

Abstract

Understanding the function of protein complexes requires information on their molecular organization, specifically, their oligomerization level. Optical super-resolution microscopy can localize single protein complexes in cells with high precision, however, the quantification of their oligomerization level, remains a challenge. Here, we present a Quantitative Algorithm for Fluorescent Kinetics Analysis (QAFKA), that serves as a fully automated workflow for quantitative analysis of single-molecule localization microscopy (SMLM) data by extracting fluorophore “blinking” events. QAFKA includes an automated localization algorithm, the extraction of emission features per localization cluster, and a deep neural network-based estimator that reports the ratios of cluster types within the population. We demonstrate molecular quantification of protein monomers and dimers on simulated and experimental SMLM data. We further demonstrate that QAFKA accurately reports quantitative information on the monomer/dimer equilibrium of membrane receptors in single immobilized cells, opening the door to single-cell single-protein analysis.

Introduction

One of the key applications of fluorescence microscopy in cell biology is to quantify biological processes in cells. Obtaining quantitative information using optical microscopy is fundamentally challenging due to the diffraction limit, setting the spatial resolution of the microscope at approximately half the wavelength of light. This limit hinders the ability to resolve isolated single molecules that are closer than ~ 200 nm. In recent years, single-molecule localization microscopy (SMLM) has emerged as a broadly used method to achieve near-molecular spatial resolution¹. Successful variants of SMLM include photoactivated localization microscopy (PALM)²,

stochastic optical reconstruction microscopy (STORM)³, *direct* STORM (*d*STORM)⁴, ground state depletion microscopy followed by individual molecule return (GSDIM)⁵ and DNA points accumulation for imaging in nanoscale topography (DNA-PAINT)⁶. The main idea behind SMLM is to reconstruct a super-resolution image by capturing a set of sparse fluorescent molecules and determining their positions at high precision. In a densely labeled sample, this sparsity can be generated by either using photoswitchable fluorophores or transiently binding labels¹. Consequently, the positions of all molecules are used to computationally generate a high-resolution image⁷.

SMLM can achieve a lateral spatial resolution down to about 10-20 nanometer by sequential emitter localization, which is sufficient to enable observation of nanoscale protein clusters. However, revealing information on the molecular organization *within* clusters requires additional analysis. At low cluster densities, photobleaching experiments can relate the number of fluorophore bleaching steps to the number of proteins within a cluster⁸. However, at high cluster densities, photobleaching analysis is hampered by overlapping point spread functions. A possible solution is the combination of SMLM with the read-out of single-molecule kinetic information on fluorophore photoswitching or repetitive transient binding of labels to a target structure, summarized as quantitative SMLM (qSMLM)⁹. A very simple approach is to relate the emission events of fluorophores (“blinking”) to a kinetic model¹⁰⁻¹². This approach has successfully reported on low-oligomeric protein organization in super-resolved protein clusters¹³⁻¹⁵.

An important quantity of interest is the stoichiometry of the oligomeric state of protein clusters. This can be extracted from an SMLM experiment by fitting the experimental blinking data to a model of the fluorophore blinking kinetics. A basic model of blinking kinetics consists of four states¹⁶: non active, active (“ON time”), dark (“OFF time”) and bleached. The blinking kinetics of

a single molecule can be modeled as a Poisson process with exponentially distributed intervals between active states. The total number of blinking events of a single emitter is geometrically distributed with a fluorophore-dependent bleaching probability^{11,16}.

Finding the parameters of these distributions is an inconvenient process⁹ and the results are highly dependent on localization quality and on the experimental setup. For example, a blinking event in one experiment might be considered noise in another experiment, due to a different noise level. This may lead to undercounting or overcounting of blinking events and eventually to inference of a bad model for the data. Learning the parameters of the ON and OFF time distributions is even more challenging because they vary as a function of illumination intensity, which is related to the position of the molecules within the illumination beam. After the experimental data is collected and filtered, the next step is to fit the blinking histogram with a dedicated kinetic model, which first requires determining the bleaching probability of the chosen fluorophores. c Finally, we can estimate the fractions of different populations in a sample by extracting the distribution of certain model parameters and fitting to the expected distribution from the kinetic model.

In practice, researchers often combine different software, each specialized on a different stage of analysis, for optimal results¹⁷. In most cases, additional manual analysis is needed in order to filter outliers and improve the accuracy. The transitions between different software and the limitations of manual analysis slow down analysis time and make the analysis of large amounts of data challenging.

Here, we developed a fast, robust, integrated and fully automated software, called “Quantitative Algorithm for Fluorescent Kinetics Analysis” (QAFKA), to extract quantitative information by analyzing the blinking events of single emitters in an SMLM data set. Specifically, we focus on

determining the stoichiometry of two different oligomeric protein populations from experimental PALM data. First, QAFKA localizes clusters in the PALM video. Second, it extracts relevant emission features, such as the histogram of emission events (“blinking” histograms), and finally QAFKA provides the stoichiometry estimation based on a model fitting process done by a deep neural network. We demonstrate the capabilities of QAFKA on simulated data as well as on experimental data, and show that it exhibits higher prediction accuracy and orders of magnitude faster run-time than other state of the art methods.

Results

QAFKA is an end-to-end solution, receiving a raw PALM video as input, and providing the final stoichiometry estimation as output. The software is divided into three main blocks (Figure 1): (i) localization, (ii) feature extraction and (iii) model fitting. The implementation of the last block can be based on deep neural network or statistical parameter estimation methods; both approaches are explored here.

We next describe the analysis pipeline at high level (for a detailed description see SI). The localization block first performs pre-processing, which includes signal-to-noise estimation, denoising, and removal of non-blinking spots, e.g. fluorescent beads. Afterwards, we filter the frames prior to the activation of the laser. Next, each frame is scanned for potential blinking events. A high intensity pixel is considered as a potential blink (the threshold is determined by analyzing intensity statistics throughout the video) and this region of interest is fitted to a 2D Gaussian. Gaussians with low fit quality are excluded from further analysis, and the remaining localizations are evaluated by the feature extraction block.

Figure 1. Algorithm block diagram of QAFKA. The input is a PALM movie containing stochastic blinking events of single molecules. The automated analysis algorithm localizes each cluster, extracts relevant emission features, and finally predicts the stoichiometry of monomers and dimers using a deep neural network.

In the feature extraction block we define the center of mass of each fitted Gaussian as the super-resolved localization of the cluster. Then, we perform merging, namely assigning adjacent localizations in different frames to the same cluster. The default merging radius is the size of a single pixel of the input video, in our case we defined it to be $\sim 150\text{nm}$, however this parameter could be tuned to fit different cluster density. Finally, a counting algorithm extracts the relevant features for the model parameters; in our case, we found that the histogram of blinking events per cluster is sufficient for learning the stoichiometry of two oligomeric states in a sample. Nonetheless, utilizing additional information, e.g. relating to blinking interval statistics, might be beneficial for the performance of QAFKA (Fig. 2).

The last block of QAFKA is based on a deep neural network (DNN) that receives as input the extracted features and outputs the stoichiometry – namely the ratio between monomers and dimers in the sample. In principle, this part could require a large database consisting of many PALM

experiments, however we took the approach of numerically simulating the dataset, according to the four-state model, which proved to produce excellent results. To evaluate the performance of the neural network, we first tested it on simulated data (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Simulated data analysis. Prediction mean error as a function of the number of clusters in the simulated experiments. We compare between the neural network (gray) and statistical parameter estimation method (white).

For each simulation, we set the fraction of proteins that occur as monomers or dimers and simulated PALM videos based on the kinetic model discussed earlier (see PALM video simulation section in the SI for full description). We then used QAFKA to localize emitters and extract relevant features that would be used in the final estimation block. Specifically, the features include the histogram of the number of blinking events, as well as the number of inter-blink intervals that are longer than 25 seconds. Finally, we input the extracted features to the neural net and calculated

the prediction error between the output and the ground truth stoichiometry using mean absolute difference. This result was compared to state-of-the-art statistical parameter estimation, namely, the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE). The inputs for the MLE are the histogram of the number of blinking events, the bleaching probability and the detection efficiency. Figure 2 shows that the DNN consistently outperformed the statistical parameter estimation method in terms of accuracy.

Note that obtaining blinking histograms usually requires additional manual analysis, i.e. finding and selecting proper localization clusters. Therefore, analyzing large databases is practically impossible without using fully automated methods such as QAFKA. The mean error was calculated over 15 independent simulated experiments per different number of clusters. The simulated mean SNR (mean peak intensity divided by mean noise intensity) for all the experiments was 5 and the simulated cluster density was 0.5 clusters per squared micron. The mean prediction error of the DNN when using 128 simulated clusters is 5.71% compared to a prediction error of 12.14% in the statistical parameter estimation method. As expected, the prediction accuracy of both methods improves as the number of clusters is increased. To validate QAFKA's performance on experimental data, we analyzed four different samples (Figure 3). First, we analyzed single-molecule data of monomeric mEos3.2 proteins immobilized on a poly-L-lysine glass surface¹². As expected, QAFKA analysis revealed exclusively monomers and excluded the existence of dimers (Figure 3A, 3C). Next, a genetic dimer of mEos3.2 was analyzed that was previously shown to consist of $18 \pm 4.5\%$ monomers and $82 \pm 4.5\%$ dimers¹² (Figure 3C). QAFKA reveals a dimer fraction of $67 \pm 6\%$, after considering the effect of the detection efficiency of the fluorescent protein (see calculations in the SI).

In addition to *in vitro* data, we tested QAFKA with monomer and dimer fractions *in cellulo*. We analyzed qPALM data of CD86 and CTLA-4 membrane proteins fused with mEos3.2 and

transfected in HeLa cells¹². For monomeric CD86-mEos3.2 proteins, QAFKA estimated a stoichiometry of $98.1 \pm 4\%$ monomers (Figure 3C). In contrast, QAFKA analysis of dimeric CTLA-4-mEos3.2 proteins predicted almost exclusively dimers ($98.6 \pm 6\%$, Figure 3B, 3C), considering a detection efficiency of 78% for mEos3.2¹² (see SI).

Figure 3. Validation of QAFKA on experimental data. (a) Temporal stack of monomer-only experiment containing mEos3.2 immobilized on a cover slip (scale bar = $5 \mu\text{m}$). (b) Temporal stack of a HeLa cell expressing dimeric membrane-bound CTLA-4-mEos3.2 (scale bar = $5 \mu\text{m}$). (c) The stoichiometry estimations of QAFKA on four different experiments with different stoichiometries. Gray (white) bars correspond the estimated percentage of monomers (dimers), red dashed line marks the expected value, and black lines mark error bars of ± 1 standard deviation (see SI for error calculation method).

Although most of QAFKA estimations were accurate, in the mixed-population sample on a coverslip the stoichiometry estimation was somewhat different from the expected value (Fig 3C). The fact that the true stoichiometry was calculated from an SDS-gel with limited accuracy might explain this discrepancy. Nonetheless, to validate the performance of QAFKA on various of monomer/ dimer ratios we have analyzed an additional experiment containing different ratios on

a glass surface. The results of these experiments reassured us that QAFKA maintains consistent accuracy for different mixtures of monomers and dimers (see SI for more information).

Besides the excellent performance of QAFKA in experimental data, it is important to note that QAFKA analysis is much faster than the commonly used manual analysis. For example, full analysis (from TIFF video to stoichiometry prediction) of a blinking movie with 12,000 frames and 251x257 pixels that contains ~20,000 potential blinking events and ~1,500 different clusters would take QAFKA less than 8 minutes. Assuming manual filtering of blinking events takes a few seconds per event, QAFKA analysis time is about two orders of magnitude faster than the manual analysis (neglecting the runtime of the localization and data fitting software and the transitions between them which increase the duration of traditional analysis).

Finally, we sought to apply QAFKA for single-cell analysis of the oligomerization of a plasma membrane receptor. We analyzed qPALM data of CRISPR/Cas12a-edited HEK293T cells that endogenously express the receptor tyrosine kinase MET fused to mEos4b¹⁸ (Figure 4A) in the presence and absence of hepatocyte growth factor (HGF). HGF is the native ligand of MET and induces oligomerization of MET receptors from monomeric to dimeric state¹⁹, and is therefore expected to increase the ratio of receptor dimers-to-monomers when added to the sample. The cumulative distribution function of the number of blinking events per cluster received from QAFKA indeed indicates higher number of blinking events in HGF-stimulated cells (Figure 4B).

Quantitative analysis with QAFKA was performed and analyzed assuming a total detection efficiency of 64% consisting of the labeling efficiency of MET with mEos4b (81%) and the detection efficiency of mEos4b in cells due to maturation (79%)¹⁸. Considering this detection efficiency (64%), QAFKA reported that in the resting state, $26 \pm 4\%$ of MET-mEos4b appeared as dimer (Figure 4C). The dimer fraction increased substantially by adding 1 nM HGF to the

sample, estimating $64 \pm 4\%$ dimers (Figure 4C). This is consistent with the general accepted mechanism of ligand-induced dimerization of receptor tyrosine kinases²⁰.

Figure 4. Oligomerization state of HGF-stimulated and unstimulated MET-mEos4b receptors in a stable HEK293T cell line. (a) Sum over time of a PALM experiment of a single HEK293T cell (marked with white dashed line) that expresses MET-mEos4b (scale bar = 2.5 μm). The oligomerization state of MET-mEos4b was analyzed with QAFKA in resting and HGF-stimulated cells. (b) Cumulative density function of the number of blinking events without ligand stimulation and in presence of 1 nM HGF. (c) Estimation of monomer and dimer fractions with QAFKA in absence and presence of 1 nM HGF.

Conclusion

Quantitative approaches in SMLM introduce challenges not only on the biological side but also in the process of evaluation. On the biological side, criteria such as stoichiometric labelling and endogenous expression of the target protein must be guaranteed in order to make quantitative statements. On the evaluation side, important parameters such as bleaching probability or detection efficiency must be estimated or determined to obtain meaningful results. We have determined the bleaching probability of the used proteins by drawing the number of blinking histograms of pure monomeric samples and fitting them to a geometric distribution. Nonetheless, QAFKA has enabled us to estimate the stoichiometry without knowing the bleaching probability, by training the DNN on histograms of different bleaching probability values. However, this comes with a price of a small loss in accuracy. To demonstrate this ability, we have generated simulated histograms of different monomer/dimer ratios with different bleaching probabilities. Then we compared ratio estimations of two neural networks: a neural network which was trained on simulated data containing the same bleaching probability as the test example; and a neural network that was trained on simulated data with varying bleaching probability values in the interval [0.25, 0.65]. Then we repeated this experiment on three different numbers of simulated clusters. The prediction errors of the second network were: 7.9%, 5.8%, and 4.1%, for 128, 256, and 512 simulated clusters respectively; note that this is ~1.5 times higher (worse) than the performance of the first neural network 5.71%, 4.38% and 2.94% for 128, 256, and 512 simulated clusters.

In the past, this analysis of the individual blinking events per single molecule was evaluated manually, which is very time-consuming. The automated quantification tool presented here, QAFKA, allows rapid analysis of single-molecule data and shows accurate stoichiometry estimations. Using simulated data, we were able to show that QAFKA surpasses manual analysis

in terms of time and accuracy. In addition, it must be mentioned that manual analyses are not possible from about 10,000 evaluated clusters onwards due to the high expenditure of time. However, QAFKA can handle a very large amount of data in a shorter time and therefore enables a more accurate stoichiometry determination thanks to the large statistics.

Experimental data have shown that QAFKA can produce accurate and reliable results. QAFKA was able to clearly identify individual monomeric mEos3.2 molecules, as well as mixtures of monomers and dimers *in vitro*. In cells, the stoichiometry of reference proteins, which form exclusively monomers or dimers, could be determined with almost complete accuracy. This makes QAFKA a valuable tool for interesting biological questions regarding the stoichiometry of protein complexes. To analyze an exciting biological question, we focused on the oligomerization of the receptor tyrosine kinase MET. MET receptors are involved in many cellular functions such as: cellular motility, cell differentiation, cell adhesion and more²¹. A recent study has demonstrated that the dimer fraction increases with the addition of the natural ligand, HGF¹⁸. This is also consistent with similar studies that focused on MET clustering after ligand addition^{22,23}. QAFKA was able to reproduce these results, orders of magnitude faster, and thus has shown its enormous applicability to biological questions.

Blinking characteristics of fluorescent proteins are largely independent of the molecular environment. In contrast, organic fluorophores are more sensible to the environment and exhibit a complex blinking characteristic²⁴. However, organic fluorophores can also be used for quantitative SMLM if the organic fluorophore binding site is shielded from the cellular environment such as in a protein tag¹⁵. Future experiments with organic fluorophores bound to a target protein via a protein tag could thus be analyzed and evaluated using QAFKA.

Another promising future direction would be to use the combination of QAFKA with the generation of stable cell lines for other membrane proteins. This combination is exceptionally well suited for the analysis of quantitative information due to the stoichiometric labelling and endogenous expression of the target protein. A work plan would look like the following: (i) use genetic engineering tools to produce stable cell lines, (ii) record qPALM movies of the fluorescently-labeled target proteins, and (iii) then analyze them with QAFKA. Hence, we see a strong potential in QAFKA for future biological questions, as it guarantees simple, fast and precise quantitative analysis. QAFKA code is available on <https://www.clever-microscopy.com/>.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

The supplementary information is available free of charge.

In this file you may find additional information regarding the pre-processing of the input data, such as denoising, data filtration and extraction of the number of blinking events. We also include information about post processing of the neural network output based on the detection efficiency of the used fluorophores. Finally, we describe the prediction error calculation throughout the paper.

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Authors Contribution

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgment

M.H., M.S.D. and T.B. acknowledge funding by the Volkswagen Foundation (grant 91067-9), LOEWE (FCI), and the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (grant SFB807). A.S. and E.N. have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 802567 -ERC- Five-Dimensional Localization Microscopy for Sub-Cellular Dynamics. L.E.W. and Y.S. are supported by the Zuckerman Foundation.

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Table of Contents graphic

